

RESILIENCE OF ENERGY INFRASTRUCTURE IN WARTIME. ASSESSMENT METHODS AND PATHWAYS FOR IMPROVEMENT

The resilience of energy infrastructure is a critical factor in ensuring the stability of energy systems, especially in wartime. In the context of the war in Ukraine, this problem has become one of the most important, after the aggression by Russia is systematically trying to destroy the country's energy infrastructure. Attacks on energy facilities, in particular missile strikes, cyberattacks, sabotage, threaten not only a stable electricity supply, but also the overall functionality of the country, including the medical sector, transport and other critical infrastructure. In this context, assessing the resilience of energy facilities is of utmost importance to prevent or minimize the consequences of such attacks. The resilience of energy facilities can be configured as their ability to adapt to changing conditions, withstand external threats and quickly recover from failures.

Key criteria for resilience in wartime are:

- Resistance to physical damage (e.g., missile or drone strikes).
- Integration of early warning systems (including SCADA – Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition).
- Ability to operate in an autonomous mode (using microgrids or mobile energy sources).
- Introduction of renewable energy sources (RES – wind, solar, biogas plants).

Another aspect is the adaptability of energy facilities, i.e. their ability to change operating modes depending on changing conditions. In wartime, when CI is often exposed to sources of damage, it is important that energy systems can operate autonomously or with alternative energy sources [1]. This may include the use of mobile generators, solar panels or wind turbines. The adaptability of the system allows to minimize energy losses and ensure uninterrupted energy supply even in the event of destruction of the main sources. The speed of recovery after damage is another important indicator of resilience. In wartime, when any support can have serious consequences, rapid recovery of energy facilities is critical. The use of backup energy sources and the availability of effective response mechanisms will not allow for the rapid recovery of destroyed infrastructure. Modeling various failure scenarios and the use of modern mathematical modeling methods, such as MC methods or probability

analysis, do not allow for the prediction of risks and optimization of recovery.

Various methods are used to assess the resilience of energy facilities in wartime. One of the main ones is system analysis, which allows for the identification of key nodes of the energy network that are critical for its functioning. Graph theory, in particular, makes it possible to model the structure of the energy network and identify vulnerabilities that may become targets of attacks. Engineering assessment methods involve the modeling of extreme scenarios that take into account physical damage to facilities, as well as the use of technical means to increase their resilience. Mathematical modeling is also used to predict possible scenarios and assess the probability of damage to key infrastructure elements. For example, models that estimate the probability of failure of energy network components allow developing strategies to minimize these losses. In addition, big data (Big Data) and machine learning technologies allow for real-time monitoring and definitively detecting anomalies, allowing for a rapid response to emerging threats.

Another important aspect is the integration of renewable energy sources (RES), such as solar and wind power plants, as well as the development of microgrids that can operate independently of the main power grid. The implementation of such technologies allows for energy security to be reduced, ensuring dependence on central energy sources and ensuring autonomy even in the event of serious damage to the main infrastructure. All these methods and approaches do not allow for increasing the resilience of energy facilities in war conditions, but for effective application, international cooperation and the implementation of uniform standards for risk assessment and management are also necessary. Developing clear protocols for responding to attacks, training personnel, and integrating new technologies into energy systems are necessary steps to increase their resilience and efficiency[2].

In conclusion, Ukraine's experience in ensuring the resilience of energy facilities in wartime can be valuable to other countries facing similar challenges. The integration of innovative technologies, the development of renewable energy sources, and the improvement of monitoring systems not only increase the resilience of energy systems, but also ensure energy security in global crisis situations.

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2. Ukrhydroenergo. (2024). Ukrhydroenergo estimates losses from Russian attacks at over 3 billion euros [Press release]. <https://www.italaw.com/sites/default/files/case-documents/italaw181408.pdf>

ЗАЯВКА НА УЧАСТЬ В КОНФЕРЕНЦІЇ

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